

Article

The Illuminated Garden—The Visitation in the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez (BPR, II/2104)

Aida Ferri ^{1,*} and Rubén Gregori ^{2,3,*}

¹ Escuela de Doctorado, Universidad Católica de Valencia San Vicente Mártir and IVEMIR-UCV (Institut Isabel de Villena d'Estudis Medievals i Renaixentistes), 46001 Valencia, Spain

² IVEMIR-UCV, Universidad Católica de Valencia San Vicente Mártir, 46001 Valencia, Spain

³ Facultad de Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades, Universidad Internacional de La Rioja, 26006 Logroño, Spain

* Correspondence: aida.ferri@ucv.es (A.F.); ruben.gregori@ucv.es (R.G.)

Abstract: This article examines the unique depiction of the Visitation in the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez, housed in the Biblioteca del Palacio Real de Madrid and also known as the Book of Hours of Isabella the Catholic. While the Visitation is a common theme in other Books of Hours, this manuscript's rendition stands out for its inclusion of visual elements not found in other works by the same illuminator. Through a detailed iconographic analysis, the article emphasizes the significance of the Visitation scene, exploring its visual components and their implications for understanding the spiritual and cultural context of the era. The study aims to highlight the Visitation miniature as a prime example of imagery crafted to serve the inner devotion of its first owner, Juana Enriquez. Ultimately, this research offers a deeper appreciation of the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez as a product of its time, designed for meditation and contemplation.

Keywords: Book of Hours; Juana Enriquez; Visitation; garden

Citation: Ferri, Aida, and Rubén Gregori. 2024. The Illuminated Garden—The Visitation in the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez (BPR, II/2104). *Religions* 15: 1238. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel15101238>

Academic Editor: Katharine Olson

Received: 30 August 2024

Revised: 7 October 2024

Accepted: 9 October 2024

Published: 12 October 2024

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction¹

The image of Isabella I of Castile (1451–1504) is often associated with that of a cultured queen who championed the fine arts as both a patron and collector, particularly known for her love of books. Recent research has revealed that she owned an impressive library and a significant collection of illuminated manuscripts. However, Isabella never had a formal library set up in a dedicated location with organized shelving and designated for public or scholarly use. Due to the itinerant nature of the royal court and the multiple royal residences, her books, like her other possessions, were dispersed and managed by servants, preventing them from ever being consolidated into a single, organized collection (Ruiz García 2003, p. 54).

Nevertheless, various inventories reveal that most of the books in the queen's personal collection were predominantly religious in content. Among these, a specific subset stands out, consisting of works intended for liturgical ceremonies and various devotional practices. Ruiz García (2004, p. 221) has termed this category "prayer books" due to their primary purpose. This series includes various types of texts, such as breviaries, devotional books, diurnals, Books of Hours, missals, passionaries, and psalters.

As Javier Docampo Capilla (2012, pp. 226–27) points out, among all the books listed in the queen's inventories, illuminated manuscripts are the most difficult to identify. This is because the descriptions tend to focus primarily on the details of the bindings, which may have changed over the centuries, rather than on the content itself. Additionally, since these are liturgical texts, which can sometimes be repetitive, the task becomes even more challenging. It is also important to consider that there are manuscripts of significant importance that either do not appear in the inventories of Isabella or simply cannot be identified. However, their ownership can be verified through a detailed study of the manuscript, considering various factors, such as coats of arms, personalized annotations,

calendars and saints' days, language, and so on. Conversely, a work initially belonging to the monarch may, upon investigation, reveal that it was not originally created for her.

Among the collection of Books of Hours belonging to the queen, we will focus on the one known as the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez (BPR, II/2104). This manuscript, held at the Biblioteca del Palacio Real de Madrid, is regarded as one of its most prized treasures. The iconography of its miniatures is unusual within the body of work of its creator, Willem Vrelant (15th century–1481). This is because the pictorial program was created with consideration of who would be its owner, Juana Enriquez (1425–1468), mother of Ferdinand the Catholic (1452–1516).

Like all Books of Hours, this one includes details and elements that were meant to be recognizable to its owner. Among all the miniatures, the Visitation stands out for incorporating a series of features that have not been addressed in previous studies and which we consider highly revealing. The Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez is a product of its time and is adorned with a series of visual and mnemonic elements that served the purpose of meditation and contemplation. In this case, the manuscript reflects the personal and spiritual goals of its owner through a personalized iconography. Unlike other works by Vrelant, the Visitation in this manuscript reveals a special intentionality, suggesting that Juana Enriquez herself was taken into consideration when creating these images.

The specific interest in studying this visual motif in the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez lies in the fact that the depiction of the Visitation departs significantly from Vrelant's traditional representations, providing insight into how the owner could have influenced the configuration of the iconographic program. A Book of Hours is not merely a luxurious devotional object; it is also a personalized tool that facilitated private prayer. Through specific visual elements, it promoted a more immersive meditative experience, highlighting the close relationship between art and devotion within the context of courtly life. The Visitation, as will be shown, includes a series of visual resources that were understood by its reader.

Furthermore, the study of this manuscript offers a key contribution to the understanding of private devotion in the Late Middle Ages, where religious objects were designed not only for embellishment but also as instruments to catalyze deep spiritual experiences. This iconographic analysis also emphasizes how the visual elements present in this Book of Hours facilitated private prayer and meditation, making it a highly significant object for medieval art history.

Therefore, the main objective of this article will be to demonstrate, through the scene of the Visitation in the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez, that certain visual themes were infused with symbolic elements that facilitated the process of private prayer, making the meditative process easier to undertake. This not only enriches our understanding of Willem Vrelant's work but also of how Books of Hours played a central role in the spiritual lives of historically significant figures like Juana Enriquez.

In the first part of this article, a contextualization of the manuscript will be provided, a necessary step for understanding why this version of the Visitation is so distinctive. In the second part, iconographic analysis of the Visitation will be explored; first from a general perspective and then focusing specifically on the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez, highlighting its importance in the context of medieval art and private devotion.

2. The Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez

It is likely that this manuscript was given to the young Isabella as part of a wedding gift from her future husband, Ferdinand. Along with the Book of Hours, the gift included an elaborate necklace intended to serve both as a component of the dowry and as a token of affection (Gómez del Pulgar Escudero 2004, p. 127).

The necklace featured seven balas rubies, a variant of spinel, set in individual flower-shaped mounts enameled in red and white, interspersed with oval grayish pearls. Hanging from its central section was a larger cabochon-cut balas ruby, polished to a high sheen,

along with a large pear-shaped pearl. The centerpiece, known as the *Codol magno*, was reputed to have belonged to King Solomon (Gómez-Chacón 2022, p. 5).

Regarding the manuscript, it was a gift from both her husband Ferdinand and the city of Zaragoza (Gómez del Pulgar Escudero 2004, p. 127). It is lavishly decorated, featuring 72 full-page miniatures and 24 smaller ones corresponding to the calendar (depicting the months and zodiac signs). The full-page miniatures appear on the verso of each folio, and their arrangement does not follow a chronological order within each series. Instead, the themes are mixed in an arbitrary fashion. The manuscript comprises a total of 365 folios, made of vellum, and measures 227 × 140 mm. The pages are written in a single column with 17 lines per folio, using both textual Gothic and rounded Gothic scripts. The decorated folios are adorned with floral borders featuring animals, birds, angels, and people (Clark 1997; González Zymila and Blasco 2016, p. 6).

The organization of the texts and prayers in this manuscript stands out for its exceptional nature, indicating that it was crafted as a unique work intended for a specific individual, deviating from the more standardized patterns found in other Books of Hours. Its uniqueness is not only evident in the beauty and richness of its miniatures but also in their remarkable quantity. This Book of Hours features an unusually high number of texts, which explains the large number of miniatures, surpassing what is typical for such works.

Although it is also known as the Book of Hours of Isabella the Catholic, the monarch was neither its first owner, nor was it created specifically for her. It belonged to Juana Enriquez, her mother-in-law, who is depicted as a young woman with fair skin and golden hair on folios 37v, 343v, and 360v. Additionally, the Latin name Johanna appears in the text on four occasions (f. 356r, 357r, 358r, and 359r). López-Valdemoro de Quesada (1910, p. 71) believed that these inscriptions were added later. Subsequently, López Serrano (1969, p. 27) suggested that it seemed an earlier name might have been erased to make way for the new one. However, there is no evidence to support this hypothesis. A close examination reveals no discernible difference in the handwriting between the instances of “Johanna” and the rest of the text (see Supplementary Materials).

On folio 343v, the book’s owner is depicted in a palatial setting, kneeling before a prie-dieu, on which rests a devotional text, highlighted by an angelic intercessor (Figure 1). The scene, although richly detailed, features minimal furniture, creating a sense of isolation for the worshiper and fostering an atmosphere of introspection in line with the ideals of the *devotio moderna*. Indeed, Books of Hours played a significant role in exemplifying the new Northern spirituality, blending text and image. Furthermore, they served as symbols of prestige in both private and public spaces, which explains the presence of this type of devotional texts in female environments (Reinburg 2012; López Montilla 2012; Peirats and Gregori 2023).

Women in the Middle Ages were closely linked to the religious sphere, and queens from the royal court took the lead in promoting monastic and conventual institutions, as well as sacred art. The case of María de Luna (ca. 1353–1406), consort of Martin I of Aragon (1356–1410), is particularly interesting, as she promoted the creation of several breviaries and surrounded herself with various devotional codices (Planas Badenas 2015; García Herrero and Muñoz Fernández 2017, pp. 16–48). Juana Enriquez’s predecessor, Maria of Castile (1401–1458), had been a model queen, concerned with her image as an aristocratic lady and aware of her role as a prototype for other women of the high nobility. The memory of this sovereign, her political efforts, and her active artistic promotion had to remain present in the collective consciousness. As the new queen, Juana Enriquez was expected to serve as an example to aristocratic ladies, just as her predecessors had, and one of her expected qualities was religious patronage. A notable example of this was the support she gave to the Barcelona convent of Jerusalem, founded under the invocation of Saint Mary of Jerusalem in the mid-15th century. This conventual complex experienced significant growth under the direction of Queen Juana Enriquez, who oversaw the commissioning of work on the church and cloister.²

Nevertheless, her religious inclination was not as prominent as her political interests, due to the Catalan Civil War (1462–1472), and she did not play as significant a role as Maria of Castile or Isabella the Catholic. In this context, illuminated codices served a dual purpose: on the one hand, they were purely religious, and on the other, they were propagandistic. These were not only devotional manuscripts and guides for private prayer and contemplation, but they also stood as true works of art, serving both in private and public settings. Thus, an image was cultivated of a queen committed to religious duties, while also setting an example for other noblewomen (García Herrero 2015, pp. 27–48).

Figure 1. Juana Enriquez kneeling in prayer with an interceding angel, Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez, fol. 343v, ca. 1447–1468, © Biblioteca del Palacio Real de Madrid.

Moreover, the Book of Hours may have played a crucial role in legitimizing the queen's image following the death of Prince Charles of Viana (1421–1461), son of her husband, John II (1398–1479). Rumors regarding Juana Enriquez's involvement in the prince's death were damaging her position. Through various channels, the monarchs orchestrated a series of

mechanisms to construct an ideal image of the rulers, highlighting key aspects of good governance (Ruiz Domingo 2018, pp. 104–12). At a time when religiosity was of such great importance, a piece like this manuscript served as a perfect tool for legitimizing her persona.

Returning to the Book of Hours, even though the text is written in Latin, it includes a series of titles in Catalan. These are “indicaciones explícitas referentes a las acciones que debía realizar el fiel cuando entraba en el interior de una iglesia, a través de rúbricas redactadas en lengua vernácula” (Planas Badenas 2020a, p. 14). These instructions appear on folios 21v–22r and consist of prayers to be recited within a sacred space. Among the rubrics, penned in gold ink and written in Catalan, one can find phrases such as: “Com començaras a entrar per: per la esglesia diras axi com se segueix”, and “com prendras laygua beneyta diras aixi com se segueix”. These titles are rendered in gold and were penned at the same time as the rest of the text, by the same hand that transcribed the manuscript.

The calendar is in Catalan and lists the festivals specific to Barcelona, as shown in the section dedicated to the Suffrage of the Saints, which confirms this identification. Among the various saints venerated in Catalonia, notable mentions include Saint Hermenegild (September 3), Saint Tecla (September 23), and Saint Severus (November 6). Additional celebrations include the *Passio Imaginis Christi* (November 9), the dedication of Barcelona Cathedral (November 18), under the patronage of the Holy Cross (Inventio and Exaltation on April 3 and September 14), Saint Eulalia (February 12) and her second translation (July 7), and Saint George (April 23) (Planas Badenas and Docampo Capilla 2016, p. 205).

Another distinctive feature of this Book of Hours is the inclusion of two offices dedicated to the Virgin: one following the Roman use and the other in honor of the Seven Joys of Mary. While the latter is frequently included in 15th-century manuscripts, it is typically accompanied by only a few miniatures. In this manuscript, however, the Seven Joys are depicted in an unusually detailed manner, which is quite rare. In fact, Ana Domínguez notes that: “[. . .] de los numerosos Libros de Horas por mi conocidos no he encontrado en ningún otro las Horas u Oficio de la Virgen en honor de sus Siete Gozos con ocho miniaturas que corresponden al comienzo del texto y sus elementos, desde maitines a completas” (Domínguez Rodríguez 1991, p. 16).

In the manuscript, there is an extensive office dedicated to the Seven Joys of the Virgin (folios 90r–105v), and its miniatures include images that were commonly used for the Hours of the Virgin in Northern Europe (Domínguez Rodríguez 2000, p. 49). Similar examples can be found in Books of Hours associated with the Aragonese royal family: the Valencian codex; the Psalter-Book of Hours of Alfonso V the Magnanimous (London, British Library, ms. Add. 28962); the Book of Hours and *Officia Varia* of Alfonso V the Magnanimous (Naples, Biblioteca Nazionale Vittorio Emanuele III, ms. I.B 55); and a Book of Hours illuminated for a Catalan aristocrat in the court of Alfonso V the Magnanimous (Los Angeles, J. Paul Getty Museum, ms. Ludwig IX 12).³

Distinguished members of the Trastámara lineage, such as King Ferdinand of Antequera (1380–1416) and Alfonso V the Magnanimous (1396–1458), demonstrated profound devotion to the Mother of God (MacKay 1987, p. 950; Planas Badenas 2020a, pp. 19–20). Similarly, John II, son and brother of the aforementioned monarchs, along with his associates, also held a deep faith in the Virgin Mary.⁴

On folios 37v and 343v, an emblematic coat of arms is depicted. Despite the fact that there has been debate about its origins, this, combined with other elements, suggests that the book was created for Juana Enriquez, the second wife of John II and mother of Ferdinand II. While scholars such as López-Valdemoro de Quesada (1910, p. 69) and Van den Gheyn (1906, pp. 321–24) believed that the coats of arms of Aragon and Enriquez might have been painted over older designs, Bousmanne (1997, p. 184) concluded, after a thorough examination, that this was not the case. Similarly, the study by Domínguez Rodríguez, Martín Ansón, and Menéndez Pidal definitively linked the heraldic emblems with Juana Enríquez (Domínguez Rodríguez et al. 1991, pp. 21–31).

On folio 360v, there is a full-page miniature depicting the Virgin of Mercy. In this illustration, Mary, with the assistance of two angels, opens her mantle to offer protection and shelter to penitent sinners (Figure 2). To the right, the ecclesiastical realm is represented with prominent religious figures such as a bishop or cardinal and other Christian figures—some of whom are visibly tonsured. To the left, the courtly realm is shown, featuring a young prince in a cape and a king with a prominent crown. In the foreground, kneeling before the Virgin, is a young woman, identified as the owner of this Book of Hours. The figures of the monarchs clearly differentiate the youthful queen from the mature king (López Serrano 1969, p. 27). This distinction appears intentional, reflecting the age difference between them—John II was 49 at the time of their marriage in 1447, while Juana Enriquez was only 22.

Figure 2. The Virgin of Mercy, Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez, fol. 360v, ca. 1447–1468, © Biblioteca del Palacio Real de Madrid.

Additionally, following Juana Enriquez's death in Tarragona in 1468, an inventory of her possessions was made, which includes a description matching the book under study: "Item vnes hores scrites em pergami de letra grossa nostrada molt istoriades en que y ha lo offici de la verge Maria de la creu les passis e molts altres oficijs ab dos gaffets dor ab les armes de la Senyora Reyna en los dos e en cascu dels dits gafets vn leo e lo camper desmalt negres ab cubertes de domas carmesi forrades de domas blau trepades e guarnides dor dins uno stoig de cuyro negre ab dos panys" (Steppe 1961, p. 326).

According to tradition, this manuscript belonged to the Catholic Monarchs, not just to Isabella alone. This belief is supported by a 17th-century inscription on the first folio of the codex, which states that Ferdinand and Isabella commissioned the book using treasures from the Americas. Javier Docampo, when analyzing the inventory of belongings of Isabella the Catholic, questioned whether this inscription reflected reality (Docampo Capilla 2017,

p. 117); the tradition had stipulated it belonged to Isabella, even though it actually belonged to her mother-in-law.

After Juana Enriquez's death, the manuscript passed into the possession of Ferdinand and Isabella, and subsequently to their daughter, Juana I (1479–1555). It later became part of the collections of Charles V (1500–1558) and Philip IV (1605–1665), who gifted it in 1642 to the newly appointed viceroy of Aragon, the Italian cardinal Teodoro Trivulzio (1597–1656). To commemorate this notable occasion, the manuscript was re-bound at a Milanese workshop specializing in metalwork, where Juana Enriquez's coat of arms was added. In the 18th century, King Ferdinand VI (1713–1759) purchased it from a descendant of the cardinal, named Farinelli (1705–1782), and it was placed in the Royal Chamber and later in the Biblioteca del Palacio Real, where it has been preserved to this day (Domínguez Rodríguez et al. 1991, pp. 13–14; Gonzalo Sánchez-Molero 2005, p. 176).

The Biblioteca Nacional de España dates the manuscript to the latter half of the 15th century, specifically between 1450 and 1499. Nevertheless, it is possible to narrow these dates further. Since the intended owner was Queen Juana Enriquez, the book was likely created around the time of her marriage in 1447, as she is depicted crowned alongside her husband, and before her death in 1468. The representation of her youthful appearance in contrast to the mature king suggests that it was likely from the early years of their marriage. According to Luis F. Martínez, the Book of Hours was a gift from John II to his wife on the occasion of their marriage (Martínez Montes 2022, pp. 63–64).

James Farquhar (1976, pp. 110–11) offers a similar view, noting that “[. . .] from the late 1450's to her death, Catalonia and Aragon were in turmoil; civil war, rebellions, and her son's right of succession demanded the attention of Juana Enriquez. Only during the years immediately following her marriage was there relative stability and peace in her life as Queen of Aragon and Catalonia. These years were possibly the ones when the manuscript was commissioned”.

The presence of the young man who appears in the same folio 360v beside the king presents a more complex interpretation. On the one hand, he could represent Charles of Viana, son of John II and, until that moment, his heir. He was 26 years old when his father remarried Juana Enriquez. The prince's appearance also matches the descriptions that have survived to this day, making it more plausible to consider that this could be Charles of Viana and not Ferdinand the Catholic. Given Juana's youth in the image, if her son were depicted, he would have to be a child and not an adult. Moreover, as her biological son, he could have been included by her side, not just with the king, with whom a stronger bond is established.

If the book was indeed a wedding gift or it was made around the wedding time, it could be speculated that the young man might be Prince Charles of Viana, given that the tensions between father and son had not yet erupted. Before becoming King of the Crown of Aragon, John II had been King of Navarre through his marriage to Blanche I of Navarre (1385–1441). When she passed away, she left her son Charles of Viana as her heir, although he could not assume the title without his father's approval. John perpetuated his reign, which caused the relationship with his son to deteriorate until it culminated in a war between them in 1451. However, at the time of John's marriage to Juana Enriquez, the situation between father and son had not yet worsened to such a degree. It was precisely this marriage that ultimately shattered their relationship, as the prince's supporters believed that the new union nullified John's claims to the crown of Navarre. Thus, the inclusion of Charles in the Book of Hours alongside his father could serve to legitimize the royal lineage of Navarre, as John appears crowned as monarch (Coll Juliá 1953, pp. 71–102; Ruiz Domingo 2018, pp. 104–6).

Nevertheless, at the same time, due to the complicated relationship between Charles of Viana and his father, it is also possible that the figure does not represent the prince. The absence of a heraldic element or other identifying sign makes the character's interpretation challenging, although we have attempted to offer a possible hypothesis.

Concerning the authorship of the miniatures, Willem Vrelant and his workshop have traditionally been credited. However, two miniatures do not fit his usual style and are likely the work of a different artist. These images, which are part of the Passion cycle and include the Breaking of the Gates of Hell and Christ's Descent into Limbo, are found on folios 192v and 223v, respectively. These miniatures are attributed to an associate of the Masters of the Golden Rolls, with whom Vrelant collaborated on several occasions (Bousmanne 1997, p. 185). Furthermore, Smeyers noted that the miniatures in the calendar section bear a strong resemblance to those in another illuminated Book of Hours by Vrelant, the Arenberg Hours (Malibu, J. Paul Getty Museum, ms. Ludwig IX 8) (Planas Badenas and Docampo Capilla 2016, p. 209).

Regarding Willem Vrelant,⁵ he was not an innovator but rather an artist who excelled at assimilating the contributions of his predecessors. As noted by Bousmanne (1997, p. 33), his remarkable talent lay in his ability to adapt to various artistic currents and iconographies.⁶ This adaptability led him to develop a distinctive style that became increasingly refined over time. His works were characterized by their high craftsmanship and delicate execution, reflecting meticulous attention to detail. These qualities helped him establish a reputation and secure commissions from prominent figures, including wealthy burghers, clergy, high-ranking officials, and the nobility.

Some of the miniatures featured in the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez were later replicated by Castilian and Toledan artists, reflecting the significant influence of both the manuscript and its illuminator. Indeed, many manuscripts imitate Vrelant's style. For example, the depiction of the Last Supper (fol. 118v) in a Spanish manuscript created for Isabella the Catholic (Cambridge (Mass.), Houghton Library, Typ. 184) demonstrates this influence. Notable mentions include the Book of Hours of Don Alfonso de Castilla, Isabel's younger brother (New York, Pierpont Morgan Library, M.854), a breviary for the Friars Minor (Paris, BNF, lat. 1064), a fragmented Book of Hours attributed to Juan de Carrión (Berlin, Kupferstichkabinett, 78 A 26 and London, B.L., Add. 50004), and the *Dialogo Político*, also made for Isabella the Catholic (Madrid, B.N., 6642) (Bousmanne 1997, p. 186).⁷

Regarding the trend of Flemish imitation in the Iberian Peninsula at the end of the 15th century, Durrieu (1893, pp. 278–79) suggested that Vrelant may have relocated to Castilian territory and worked there for a time. This question has recently been revisited by Espada Custódio (2016, p. 224), who suggests that Vrelant sought patrons in France. Upon evaluating his trajectory, there are two periods when the illuminator could have been in the French country. The first is the period between his departure from Utrecht and his settling in Bruges (1449–1451/54), and the second is between 6 May 1456, and 28 June 1459, a break during which he did not pay his contribution to the Guild of Saint John the Evangelist in Bruges. However, while these are intriguing proposals, they have yet to be confirmed by any archival documents.

According to Planas Badenas (2020b, p. 104), this manuscript is one of several examples highlighting the strong artistic connections between the northern territories of the Duchy of Burgundy and Catalonia. The Book of Hours was probably written in the Southern Netherlands by a Catalan scribe, as a direct commission from or for Queen Juana Enriquez (Planas Badenas 2020c, p. 175). Notable Catalan communities were established in major commercial centers like Bruges and Ghent: "Estas agrupaciones mercantiles gozaban del suficiente poder adquisitivo para comprar estos libros de lujo, facilitando la presencia de calígrafos de la Península Ibérica, identificables por emplear una letra gótica *rotunda*" (Planas Badenas and Docampo Capilla 2016, p. 209).

It seems clear that Juana Enriquez was the initial recipient of this Book of Hours, and thus, the artistic program was designed with her in mind. While many miniatures are noteworthy, we will focus specifically on the Visitation due to its unique characteristics. In fact, this theme is not the only one that deviates from Vrelant's usual iconographic repertoire; many of the miniatures in this manuscript differ from those in his other works. This suggests that the iconographic program was carefully considered and tailored to the

intellectual level of its owner. However, before delving into an analysis of this image, it is essential to examine the religious episode in detail.

3. The Iconographic Theme of the Visitation of the Virgin

The Visitation cycle, depicting the Virgin Mary's visit to Elizabeth, comprises five key events: Mary's journey, either accompanied by a servant or occasionally by Saint Joseph; the meeting between the two women; the Magnificat; the birth of John the Baptist; and Mary's return home after spending three months with her cousin, assisting her during childbirth.

The primary sources for this account are threefold: the Gospel of Luke (1:39–80), the Protoevangelium of James (chapter XII), and later, the Golden Legend by Jacobus de Voragine from the 13th century (chapter LXXXVI). Additionally, there are other sources, such as hymns, sermons, and literary texts like vision narratives (e.g., the *Meditationes Vitae Christi*), which expanded on the earlier narrative (García García 2017).

Of the four canonical evangelists, only Luke provides a detailed account of Mary's genealogy and life. Among other passages, he describes her visit to her cousin Elizabeth, who was married to the priest Zechariah. Elizabeth and Zechariah were said to be "childless because Elizabeth was not able to conceive, and they were both very old" (Luke 1:7), but miraculously, she became pregnant with John the Baptist. Shortly after receiving the Annunciation from the Archangel Gabriel and learning that Elizabeth was pregnant, Mary decided to visit her cousin to assist during the final months of her pregnancy. The evangelist recounts it as follows (Luke 1:39–45) <https://www.bible.com/bible/compare/LUK.1.39-49> (accessed on 1 September 2024):

"At that time Mary got ready and hurried to a town in the hill country of Judea, where she entered Zechariah's home and greeted Elizabeth. When Elizabeth heard Mary's greeting, the baby leaped in her womb, and Elizabeth was filled with the Holy Spirit. In a loud voice she exclaimed: "Blessed are you among women, and blessed is the child you will bear! But why am I so favored, that the mother of my Lord should come to me? As soon as the sound of your greeting reached my ears, the baby in my womb leaped for joy. Blessed is she who has believed that the Lord would fulfill his promises to her!"

This iconographical theme has been extensively depicted in art, from the 5th century to the present, with various interpretations.⁸ One notable version is the Byzantine depiction, where Mary and Elizabeth approach each other in a very formal and serious manner. In contrast, the Syrian version shows the cousins embracing in a more spontaneous and intimate gesture, reminiscent of the embrace between Saint Joachim and Saint Anne at the Golden Gate in Jerusalem. From the Late Middle Ages, influenced by the rise of Marian devotion and Franciscan literature in the 13th century, Western artists began to portray Elizabeth either bowing or kneeling, emphasizing the Virgin's supremacy, even though the gesture is actually directed towards the Infant Jesus (Amo Horga 2009, p. 239; Velu 2012).

Medieval depictions of the Visitation commonly centered on the two women, often set near the home of Elizabeth and Zechariah. The scene usually depicts Elizabeth coming out to meet Mary. Sometimes, only an urban backdrop, such as Nazareth, where the couple lived, is shown. Other figures may appear, such as Joseph, Zechariah, a servant, the two other Marys (Mary of Clopas and Mary Salome), or even angels. Additionally, the Magnificat may be indicated through a scroll or phylactery. The portrayal of the cousins has varied over time, ranging from a distant gesture of recognition to an embrace, kiss, or touching of the womb (Figures 3 and 4). The Visitation has been incorporated into Marian cycles and mysteries, the Infancy of Jesus, and the life of John the Baptist. By the late Middle Ages, spurred by the *devotio moderna*, this episode took on devotional values that particularly impacted the feminine sphere (Westergård 2006, pp. 69–72; García García 2017).

There are other, more realistic depictions in which the Infant Jesus and Saint John the Baptist are shown in the wombs of their respective mothers (Figure 5). The Son of God, typically depicted standing and larger in size, blesses his cousin, who is shown in a kneeling posture. This visual theme, rooted in French and German traditions,⁹ holds

significant theological importance as it prefigures John's words from the Gospel of Luke (3:16): "But one who is more powerful than I will come, the straps of whose sandals I am not worthy to untie". It may also refer to the moment when, upon hearing the Virgin's voice, the unborn John leaped for joy in Elizabeth's womb, as noted in Luke 1:39–41. While Elizabeth was the first to hear the good news, it was her unborn son who recognized the mystery. Elizabeth heard Mary with her ears, while John perceived the presence of Jesus through his own sense of joy (Universidad de Navarra 2018, p. 1067).

Figure 3. Visitation in Triptych with Scenes from the Life of the Virgin, Dirk Bouts and workshop, ca. 1445, © Museo del Prado, Madrid.

Hence, although Elizabeth and Mary proclaimed the grace, it was John who internally experienced it and expressed his joy. This is reflected in the apocryphal Protoevangelion of James (Santos Otero 2005, p. 65) and the Golden Legend, highlighting that John's recognition was an act of reverence towards his Lord and a tribute (Voragine 1982, pp. 336–37).

This episode has garnered special attention in theology, as it represents both Jesus' first journey and the recognition of his divine nature. Even in the womb, John acknowledges that the unborn Jesus is the Son of God, thus becoming an early witness to the Incarnation and divinity of Christ (García García 2017).

Artistically, the Visitation has enjoyed widespread popularity, particularly due to its emphasis on female experience. The scene, where two women embrace and share their joy about their pregnancies, became a significant literary and visual reference for women, allowing them to see themselves reflected in the narrative. This depiction of mutual support, affection, and recognition between the cousins transformed into a joyful topic well-received by female audiences. While dolorous themes from cycles like the Passion or the Stabat Mater played a crucial role in the religious life of women, there was also a

need for more uplifting and celebratory imagery. Consequently, the Visitation, unlike the Passion narratives or miraculous events like the Assumption, offered a scene where women could find themselves in the shared happiness of two friends celebrating their pregnancies (Porquieres 2013, p. 136).

Figure 4. Visitation, Rogier van der Weyden, 1435–1440, © Museum der bildenden Künste, Leipzig.

In this episode, Mary and Elizabeth take center stage, though indirectly, Jesus and John the Baptist are also involved. However, their roles differ significantly from those in the Nativity or Madonna scenes, where the Virgin is primarily a supporter or caretaker of her child. This is the only depiction where Mary appears alongside another woman by her own choice, not out of necessity or directly related to her child. While the reason for their meeting is Elizabeth's pregnancy, it differs from the crucifixion scene where Mary is with the other two Marys due to Christ's impending death. Here, the motivation is more personal—Mary goes to assist Elizabeth with the birth. Therefore, literary and visual sources emphasizing this episode highlight the joy of both women, Mary's charity and tenderness in caring for her cousin, and Elizabeth's recognition of Mary as the future mother of the Son of God. In fact, this recognition is seen as a “second annunciation”, revealed to Elizabeth by the Holy Spirit (Porquieres 2013, pp. 138 and 151).

The annunciation to Zechariah about Elizabeth's pregnancy can be viewed as a preparation for Mary's own, as it involves divine intervention, disturbance, the annunciation itself, difficulty, and a sign. For instance, Zechariah, though he desired offspring, was initially barren but his prayers were answered by God. In contrast, Mary, who did not seek a child, received one through God's mediation. When the angel appeared to them, both were

troubled, though in different ways—Zechariah requested a sign, while Mary received one without asking. Additionally, the stories of these two cousins are interconnected through their setting, the Temple of Jerusalem. The Gospel of Luke begins and ends its narrative in this place, symbolizing the continuity between the salvation promised to Israel and that fulfilled in Christ (Universidad de Navarra 2018, p. 1066).¹⁰

Figure 5. Visitation, Jakob and Hans Strüb, ca. 1505, © Museo Nacional Thyssen-Bornemisza, Madrid.

Moreover, Saint Ambrose, in his *Expositio Evangelii secundum Lucam*, reflects on why the angel first appeared in the Temple to Zechariah, foreshadowing Jesus's later sacrifice. It's important to remember that Christ himself is the Temple, and when he dies, the earthly Temple is destroyed. Saint Paul notes in Hebrews 10:19–20: "Therefore, brothers and sisters, since we have confidence to enter the Most Holy Place by the blood of Jesus, by a new and living way opened for us through the curtain, that is, his body". Thus, referring to his body as the veil separating the Most Holy Place from the rest of the Temple signifies that Christ was indeed the "Holy of Holies".

4. The Visitation in the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez

In the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez, the miniature of the Visitation episode is located on folio 91v (Figure 6), between the Annunciation (folio 89v) and the Nativity (folio 93v). This placement confirms that it is part of a narrative cycle centered on both the Virgin and Jesus. Although the Visitation scene is well-represented in Western religious imagery, it was regularly found "in a clear narrative context, as part of a series of images rather than in an isolated form as a devotional image". In addition, despite being established as a liturgical feast in 1389 and becoming a Marian celebration, it also served to reflect on both the Virgin's purity and the humanity of Christ. Therefore, it was not unusual for the scene to appear in Marian and Christological cycles, with a greater prevalence in the former (Westergård 2006, pp. 73–74).

In this depiction, only Elizabeth and Mary are present. Elizabeth leans towards the Virgin and touches her womb while both women hold hands. Mary is portrayed as younger than her cousin, who has more mature features. This contrast emphasizes the miraculous nature of Elizabeth's pregnancy, given her advanced age. The scene is set outdoors, in a walled garden with various flowers, and in the background, there is a grove and several buildings. Two angels hold a red cloth with gold embellishments just behind the women, framing this moment and separating it from the rest of the scene. Vrelant follows a tradition started by the Master Boucicaut, using a system of spatial framing through hanging fabrics. This technique creates a new background, helping to establish a space by implication (Domínguez Rodríguez 1991, pp. 23–24).

Figure 6. Visitation, Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez, fol. 91v, ca. 1447–1468, © Biblioteca del Palacio Real de Madrid.

On the other hand, in addition to its visual aspect, the veil carries a symbolic meaning connected to the Incarnation. As previously mentioned, in the Old Testament the veil separated the holy space from the human, preventing entry and concealing the Holy of Holies. When Jesus dies on the cross, the veil is torn, symbolizing the removal of the barrier that had hindered access to the divine. At the same time, it alludes to the end of the separation between God's people and the Gentiles (Universidad de Navarra 2018, p. 7388). Thus, the veil represents the very flesh of Jesus, and as His flesh was torn, what had been concealed by the veil was now revealed—namely, the divinity and the truth of the Incarnate Word (Hamburger 2012, p. 284).

Thanks to this system, the viewer's attention is directed primarily towards the two women, with Mary's figure standing out due to the chromatic contrast between her blue garment and the red hanging. The sky is depicted with a checkered pattern of red, blue, and gold squares. In the center, God blesses with the orb of the world surrounded by the angelic court.

It is noteworthy that, unlike other representations of the Visitation, this one highlights the walled garden with battlements, which separates the sacred scene from the background landscape. This element is inspired by the *hortus conclusus*, a symbol of love found in the Song of Songs (Ct 4:12), which became an artistic motif associated with the Virgin. Its inclusion in art came through Flemish artists in the early 15th century and was quickly associated with female religiosity (Antoine-König 2002, specifically pp. 16–81).

The enclosed garden, inspired by Flemish gardens from the beginning of the 15th century, should be understood as a metaphor for the human soul: just as the garden requires care and maintenance—removing weeds that symbolize sin—the soul must also be nurtured and purified. In practical terms, the medieval garden was more than a tranquil space of natural beauty and contemplation; it was also a space for spiritual education and divine connection. This explains its presence in both religious and private settings, as the walled garden became a domestic space that allowed women to enjoy a private, natural, and serene environment within their homes. Furthermore, the enclosed garden symbolizes the civilized and orderly in contrast to the wild and chaotic forest, establishing a dichotomy between order and disorder (Martín Martínez de Simón 2018, pp. 49–54).¹¹

In the depiction of the Visitation, the sacred figures of Mary and Elizabeth are within the garden's perimeter, while the rest of humanity, represented by the buildings in the background, is situated in the surrounding woods. The *hortus conclusus* is portrayed as a microcosm where a miraculous encounter occurs, inviting contemplation from multiple perspectives: as a space for meditation; as a place of sacred encounter; and for the scene of the Visitation itself, which highlights Mary's virginity, the Incarnation, and the divinity of Jesus.

Moreover, the association of the enclosed garden with the soul and contemplation, as well as its reference in the Song of Songs, contributed to its identification with Mary, underscoring her restored soul, purity, and virginity. Consequently, this symbolism was adopted in art, framing both conceptual and narrative scenes featuring the Virgin. This explains why the enclosed garden is a prominent feature in the Litany of Loreto and in depictions of the Immaculate Conception (Peinado Guzmán 2012, pp. 167–90). For this reason, the garden, with its plants and flowers, plays a crucial symbolic role in the overall composition.

In the Visitation miniature, the inclusion of flowers is deliberate and meaningful. At the feet of the two women lies a sea of roses, and among them rise two stems of white lilies. These elements are not merely decorative but also part of the Litany of Loreto. The rose symbolizes discretion, charity, and suffering, connected to the Passion of Jesus; likewise, the thornless rose represents the Virgin's virginal purity. The lily represents Mary's virginity and immaculate conception. When the petals face upward, they symbolize openness to God, while petals extending sideways indicate Mary's maternal and missionary qualities (Levi d'Ancona 1977, pp. 210–20 and 330–55; Disalvo 2010, p. 134; Peinado Guzmán 2012, pp. 176–78; Salvador González 2014c, pp. 1–48; Martín Martínez de Simón 2018, pp. 51–52).

In the miniature, each lily stem bears two flowers. The stem on the left has both flowers open, while the right stem has only one in bloom. This can be interpreted as a symbolic-floral representation of the scene: the blooming stem represents Elizabeth and John, while the less-open flower symbolizes Jesus, still in an early embryonic state—although John has not yet been born, he is older than his cousin and that is why his flower is more fully open. Meanwhile, Mary is represented by the flower with petals lifted upwards, symbolizing her openness to God.

The Annunciation (folio 89v) features a vase with three lily stems, two in bloom and one yet to open (Figure 7). This imagery signifies both the purity of the Virgin and Mary's triple virginity: before, during, and after giving birth to Jesus; on the other hand,

it is a Christological symbol (Levi d'Ancona 1977, pp. 211–12). Based on the exegetical interpretation of the Jesse Tree passage (Isaiah 11:1), Mary is the stem from which the flower, Jesus, will emerge. In this way, the lily becomes a symbol that prefigures both Mary's virginity and the Incarnation (Salvador González 2013, pp. 183–222; 2014a, pp. 37–60; 2014b, pp. 75–96; 2015, pp. 2–32; Denise Fallena 2021, p. 106). The presence of three lilies could also reference the Holy Trinity: the two open flowers may represent the Father and the Son, while the bud yet to bloom symbolizes the unborn Christ.

Figure 7. Annunciation, Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez, fol. 89v, ca. 1447–1468, © Biblioteca del Palacio Real de Madrid.

Furthermore, the lily serves as a reminder of the Annunciation, so its dual presence in the Visitation scene might also suggest that this episode represents a “second Annunciation”. In this context, the fully open stem on the left refers to the initial Annunciation, when Gabriel announced Mary's pregnancy, while the partially opened lily alludes to this moment of second Annunciation through John's recognition. Consequently, the presence of both lilies could symbolize the four figures involved (noting that while the two infants are not physically depicted, they are symbolically present) and the biblical event itself.

5. The Hortus Conclusus, the Rose, and the Lily

At this point, there is no doubt that Visitation image is imbued with a series of visual messages understood by its viewer, Juana Enriquez. This iconographic theme differs from most of Vrelant's Visitation scenes, as it includes the walled garden and flowers not found in

other representations. Among the various Books of Hours associated with the illuminator Vrelant, no similar Visitation image has been identified in comparison to the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez. Despite being a recurrent theme in Books of Hours, this depiction is quite exceptional.

In Vrelant's Visitation scenes, the focus is consistently on the meeting between the two women (Figures 8–15).¹² Isabel, being older, is always shown with her hair covered, whereas the Virgin is depicted with long, golden hair. These scenes generally feature physical contact between the cousins, with Isabel typically being more inclined to initiate this contact. In some miniatures, Isabel slightly bows towards Mary, giving the Virgin a more prominent position; in other examples, they are depicted at a similar height.

Figure 8. Visitation, Hore beate marie virginis secundum consuetudine(m) romane ecclesie (ms. W.240), fol. 183v, ca. 1450–1460, © Walter Art Gallery, Baltimore.

Regarding attire, the Virgin is usually dressed entirely in blue, or at least wears a blue garment. In contrast, Isabel is depicted in reddish or warm tones, except in those images rendered in grisaille.

Concerning the meeting place, this varies from one miniature to another, though it is always set in an open space. Usually, the scene is depicted amidst nature, with distant urban landscapes, castles, or fortifications. Nevertheless, there are also compositions where the two women are shown in front of Elizabeth's house. In all these cases, nature is present with trees, shrubs, and some flowers, though sparingly. While this type of landscape is featured in the image, it holds no significant meaning. It serves merely as a decorative backdrop to frame and enhance the scene, providing a realistic context without any symbolic or individualized intent, thus differing from the Visitation in the Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez.

On the other hand, if we compare Vrelant's Visitation with that of the Book of Hours and *Officia varia* of Alfonso the Magnanimous (Naples, Bibl. Naz. Vittorio Emanuele III, ms. I. B. 55, fol. 191v), given the connections between both manuscripts (Planas Badenas and Docampo Capilla 2016, p. 206), certain similarities can be observed, such as the checkered background and the positioning of both women, with Saint Elizabeth kneeling (Figure 16).

Figure 9. Visitation, Hore secundum usum romanum (ms. W.197), fol. 76v, ca. 1460, © Walter Art Gallery, Baltimore.

Figure 10. Visitation, Horae secundum usum romane ecclesie (ms. W.220), fol. 64r, ca. 1450–1455, © Walter Art Gallery, Baltimore.

Figure 11. Visitation, Arenberg Hours (ms. Ludwig IX 8), fol. 65r, early 1460s, © The J. Paul Getty Museum, Malibu.

Figure 12. Visitation, Horae secundum consuetudinem romane ecclesiae (ms. M. 387), fol. 242v, ca. 1460, © Pierpont Morgan Library, New York.

Figure 13. Visitation, Llangattock Hours (ms. Ludwig IX 7), fol. 68v, ca. 1450, © The J. Paul Getty Museum, Malibu.

Figure 14. Visitation, Book of Hours of Queen Eleanor of Portugal (ms. Il.165), fol. 53v, ca. 1450–1475, © Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal, Lisbon.

This comparison reveals that a range of symbols understood by Juana Enriquez was employed, with flowers playing a crucial role. Their presence in an episode featuring two pregnant women emphasized the connection with the recipient, who was also a woman.

The inclusion of the *hortus conclusus*, roses, and lilies in this context facilitated meditation and, consequently, communication with the divine. This book acted as a conduit between Juana Enriquez and the divine realm, with both the text and images aiding in establishing and maintaining that link. Hence, the garden and flowers became visual tropes that expanded the message conveyed by the religious episode.

Figure 15. Visitation, Hours of Leonor de la Vega (ms. Vitr/24/2), fol. 68v, ca. 1465–1470, © Biblioteca Nacional de España, Madrid.

Figure 16. Visitation, Book of Hours and Officia Varia of Alfonso V the Magnanimous (ms. I.B 55, fol. 191v.), 1455–1458, © Biblioteca Nazionale Vittorio Emanuele III, Naples.

Moreover, these flowers served an additional purpose. The aim of this type of devotional reading, popularized by Nordic spirituality, was to contemplate God through introspective reflection, contrition, compassion, and emotion, guided by Christ, the Virgin, and the saints. Heinrich Böhmer noted that the function of private prayer was to relive the Gospels through imagination and the devoted expansion of legends and revelations, to emulate these holy figures and partake in their joys and sorrows (Böhmer 1921, pp. 40–41).

The goal was to achieve a level of closeness and familiarity that extended beyond prayer to any moment of the day, whether during work, joy, or rest. In this context, Johan Huizinga in *The Autumn of the Middle Ages* observed that: “The mind was filled with Christ to such a degree that the Christological note immediately began to sound whenever any act or thought showed even the slightest congruence with the life or suffering of the Lord. A poor nun who carries firewood to the kitchen imagines that she is carrying the Cross. The notion of carrying wood by itself is enough to bathe the activity in the bright glow of the highest act of love” (Huizinga 1996, pp. 220–21).

Accordingly, daily contemplation of a rose or lily facilitated a mental connection with the divine realm, serving as touchpoints with the Book of Hours, even if they were not directly linked to it.

This demonstrates that the use of these visual elements in manuscripts enhanced the understanding of the depicted scenes, a practice that was common due to its effectiveness in other works. For instance, in folio 14v of the Book of Hours of Mary of Burgundy, there is an image within an image: a young woman reading a Book of Hours in the foreground, and through an open window, a vision of the Virgin with the Child and the same young woman with two other girls in a church (Figure 17). It appears the reading is made real within the space of the window, and the reader, identified as Mary of Burgundy, is experiencing this event contemplatively. Notably, in the real part of the image where Mary reads, there are two carnations and a vase with irises. These elements, present in her daily life, would aid her meditative process, as, like the rose and lily, these flowers symbolize the Virgin and Jesus. Consequently, the presence of these visual tropes in the real portion of the image functioned as communicative channels, reinforcing the message. They also reveal their presence in everyday life and how their sensory contemplation contributed to creating that meditative link (Penketh 1997, p. 266; Havice 1995, p. 78).

Figure 17. The Virgin in a church with Mary of Burgundy at her devotions, Hours of Mary of Burgundy (cod. 1857), fol. 14v, ca. 1477, © Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, Vienna.

Similarly, John Decker's study of the Hours of Catherine of Cleves highlights the inclusion of jewels in the margins of images, suggesting they are simulated votive offerings designed to secure the saints' help and protection. Therefore, flowers also served as mnemonic devices aiding in meditation (Decker 2018, pp. 33–76).

6. Conclusions

As demonstrated, the Visitation serves as an excellent example of imagery designed for private prayer. While the Book of Hours includes other unique iconographic elements not found in Vrelant's works, the Visitation features a series of visual elements that resonate with the reality of Juana Enriquez, aiding her meditation process. The presence of these elements in the Visitation, a representation with significant feminine focus, suggests that it was thoughtfully created with its owner in mind. Similarly, it should also be taken into account that the variations in the manuscript may reflect regional stylistic changes or the desires of the patron.

The *hortus conclusus* and flowers were not merely decorative but carried profound meaning, supporting Juana Enriquez in her spiritual connection and meditation. Therefore, they not only enhanced the religious message when the Book of Hours was read but also allowed for a contemplative experience that could be extended to her everyday life. Visiting a home garden or having flowers at home could similarly facilitate the contemplative process, fulfilling their role as communicative channels to the divine. The example of the Book of Hours of Mary of Burgundy illustrates this perfectly, incorporating flowers in a depiction of the real world and showing how they could aid in meditation and contemplation.

Therefore, it is clear that the enclosed garden, roses, and lilies were included not just to accentuate the mysticism of the religious episode but also to function as links and connections to the divine.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://rbdigital.realbiblioteca.es/s/realbiblioteca/item/11497> (accessed on 10 September 2024), Book of Hours of Isabella the Catholic, Real Biblioteca Digital.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, A.F. and R.G.; methodology, A.F. and R.G.; software, A.F. and R.G.; validation, A.F. and R.G.; formal analysis, A.F. and R.G.; investigation, A.F. and R.G.; resources, A.F. and R.G.; data curation, A.F. and R.G.; writing—original draft preparation, A.F. and R.G.; writing—review and editing, A.F. and R.G.; visualization, A.F. and R.G.; supervision, A.F. and R.G.; project administration, A.F. and R.G.; funding acquisition, A.F. and R.G. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Data are contained within the article.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Notes

- ¹ This work is part of the I + D + i Project «Marginación e integración. Imágenes al servicio del conflicto religioso mediterráneo (siglos XIV-XVI)» (CIGE/2022/62), funded by the Conselleria d'Innovació, Universitats, Ciència i Societat Digital.
- ² From the inventory of the belongings of King John II after his death, it is known that he donated "hun retaule de talla rodona, de obre de Flandes, ab ystoria dels goigs. En les cubertes dens ha la visitatio de Sancta Elisabet" to said convent. It is possible, as Pascual Molina (2015, p. 75) suggests, that the donation was specifically linked to the memory of his wife after her death.
- ³ The Book of Hours of Juana Enriquez shares several distinctive features with others, including the inclusion of two offices dedicated to depicting the sufferings of Christ and His subsequent death: the Office of the Holy Cross and the Office of the Passion. The textual characteristics of this Book of Hours lead to iconographic variations that create a unique program, closely resembling that of the previously mentioned Psalter-Book of Hours of Alfonso V the Magnanimous. Notable examples include the Baptism of Christ (fol. 23v), the Presentation of the Virgin in the Temple (fol. 27v), Christ crucified on the cross lying on the

ground (fol. 139v), and the Presentation of Jesus in the Temple (fol. 59v). The prayer dedicated to the Guardian Angel, featuring the monarch in prayer (fol. 343v), reflects a practice specific to the Crown of Aragon from 1411. This theme is similarly depicted in the Psalter-Book of Hours of Alfonso V the Magnanimous, among others. The inclusion of two Dominican saints and Saint Francis of Assisi in the Suffrage of the Saints is indicative of the significant role these religious orders played in the political sphere of the Crown of Aragon (Planas Badenas and Docampo Capilla 2016, pp. 206–8).

- 4 We can find one example of Marian devotion in the inventory of King John II's possessions after his death. It includes three tapestries depicting the Seven Joys of Our Lady, which apparently came from the chapel of his eldest son, Charles of Viana. However, they had been in the royal family's possession since at least 1436 and were listed as belonging to King Ferdinand of Antequera. These tapestries were used to decorate the high altar of the Santa Eulalia chapel in Barcelona for the funeral services held in honor of his wife, Leonor of Albuquerque. Subsequently, they were transferred by John II to the chapel of Ferdinand II, who bequeathed them to the Royal Chapel of Granada in his will (Zalama and Molina 2012, p. 294). For further information about the Marian devotion of the monarchs of the Crown of Aragon, see (Crispí Cantón 1996, pp. 85–101; Crispí Cantón 1997, pp. 83–103; Morant Gimeno 2018, pp. 145–60).
- 5 For more information about Vrelant, see (Bousmanne 1997).
- 6 The presence of two miniatures in the manuscript under analysis demonstrates that its creator, Willem Vrelant, adapted to new iconographies even within the rigid framework of Books of Hours. These miniatures—The Funeral of the Virgin (fol. 78v) and The Stoning of Christ (fol. 106v)—are not found in any other Book of Hours associated with his work (Bousmanne 1997, p. 124). Regarding the image of the funeral of the Virgin, see (Domínguez Rodríguez et al. 1991, pp. 21–31).
- 7 Espada Custódio (2016, p. 221) considers that the Perfeitíssimas Horas of Queen Doña Leonor (Lisbon, Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal, IL. 165) were commissioned by a royal figure akin to Queen Juana Enriquez from the miniaturist Willem Vrelant. He also proposes Ferdinand the Catholic, specifically at the time of his marriage to Queen Isabella in 1469. In any case, the Book of Hours made its way to the Kingdom of Castile, at which point its miniatures would have served as a model for Juan de Carrión in creating the Book of Hours for Infante Alfonso (New York, PML, ms. M. 854). The arrival of the codex at the Portuguese court would have been assured by the successive marriages of the daughters of the Catholic Monarchs, the Infanta Isabel to Prince Alfonso (1490) and to King Manuel of Portugal (1497), or through the Infanta María, who married the same sovereign in 1500.
- 8 For further information, although focusing on Italian art, see (Westergård 2007).
- 9 The earliest examples of this distinctive iconography can be traced back to Macedonian-period Byzantine art (García García 2017).
- 10 For an in-depth exploration of the parallels between the childhoods of Jesus and John the Baptist, see Verheyden (2011, pp. 137–60).
- 11 For a detailed exploration of the symbolism of the garden, see (Gómez Anuarbe 2003).
- 12 As a comparative example, the following works attributed to Vrelant have been selected: Hore beate marie virginis secundum consuetudinem romane ecclesie (Baltimore, Walters Art Gallery, ms. W.240), Hore secundum usum romanum (Baltimore, Walters Art Gallery, ms. W.197), Horae secundum usum romane ecclesie (Baltimore, Walters Art Gallery, ms. W.220), Arenberg Hours (Malibu, J. Paul Getty Museum, ms. Ludwig IX 8), Horae secundum consuetudinem romane ecclesie (New York, Pierpont Morgan Library, ms. M. 387), Hours of Llangatock (Malibu, J. Paul Getty Museum, ms. Ludwig IX 7), Book of Hours of Queen Eleanor of Portugal (Lisbon, Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal, ms. Il.165), and Hours of Leonor de la Vega (Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional de España, ms. Vitr/24/2).

References

- Amo Horga, Luz María del. 2009. La iconografía de la Navidad. I: Ciclo de la Navidad o Encarnación. In *La Natividad: Arte, Religiosidad y Tradiciones Populares*. Coordinated by Francisco Javier Campos and Fernández de Sevilla. Madrid: Real Centro Universitario Escorial-María Cristina, pp. 233–52.
- Antoine-König, Élisabeth (curator). 2002. *Sur la terre comme au ciel. Jardins d'Occident à la fin du Moyen Âge [catalogue de l'exposition]*. Paris: Réunion des musées nationaux.
- Bousmanne, Bernard. 1997. «Item a Guillaume Wyclant aussi enlumineur». Brussels: Brepols.
- Böhmer, Heinrich. 1921. Loyola und die deutsche Mystik. *Berichte über die Verhandlungen der Sächsischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Leipzig. Philologisch-Historische. Klasse I* 73: 1–43.
- Clark, Gregory. 1997. *The Hours of Isabel la Católica and manuscript painting in Flanders in time of Philip The Good (1419–1467)*. Madrid: Biblioteca Rara.
- Coll Juliá, Núria. 1953. *Juana Enríquez, lugarteniente real en Cataluña (1461–1468)*. Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas.
- Crispí Cantón, Marta. 1996. La verònica de Madona Santa Maria i la processó de la Puríssima organitzada per Martí l'Humà. *Locus Amoenus* 2: 85–101. [CrossRef]
- Crispí Cantón, Marta. 1997. La difusió de les “Veròniques” de la Mare de Déu a les catedrals de la Corona d'Aragó a finals de l'Edat Mitjana. *Lambard* IX: 83–103.
- Decker, John R. 2018. Aid, protection, and social alliance: The role of jewelry in the margins of the Hours of Catherine of Cleves. *Renaissance Quarterly* 71: 33–76. [CrossRef]
- Denise Fallena, Rosa. 2021. Jardines en un Libro de Horas: Aspiración por el paraíso perdido. *IMAGO Revista de Emblemática y Cultura Visual* 13: 85–110. [CrossRef]

- Disalvo, Santiago. 2010. Hortus deliciarum et flos spineti: El jardín y las flores de María, de la poesía litúrgica a la lírica hispánica medieval. *Revista do Centro de Estudos Portugueses* 30: 131–51. [CrossRef]
- Docampo Capilla, Javier. 2012. La iluminación de manuscritos durante el reinado de Isabel la Católica: Nuevas consideraciones. In *La miniatura y el grabado de la Baja Edad Media en los archivos españoles*. Coordinated by María del Carmen Lacarra Ducaay. Zaragoza: Institución Fernando el Católico, pp. 225–74.
- Docampo Capilla, Javier. 2017. Manuscritos iluminados en la corte de Castilla a finales del siglo XV: Los códices de Isabel la Católica. In *Manuscrits il·luminats. La tardor de l'Edat Mitjana i els inicis del Renaixement*. Edited by Josefina Planas Badenas. Lleida: Edicions de la Universitat de Lleida, pp. 87–123.
- Domínguez Rodríguez, Ana. 1991. *Libro de Horas de Isabel la Católica*. Madrid: Patrimonio Nacional y Testimonio Compañía Editorial.
- Domínguez Rodríguez, Ana. 2000. Libros de Horas en la Corona de Castilla. Hacia un estado de la cuestión. *Anales de Historia del Arte* 10: 9–54.
- Domínguez Rodríguez, Ana, Martín Ansón, M. Luisa, and Faustino Menéndez Pidal. 1991. El libro de las horas de Isabel la Católica de la biblioteca de palacio. *Reales Sitios: Revista del Patrimonio Nacional* 110: 21–31.
- Durrieu, Paul. 1893. Manuscrit d'Espagne remarquables principalement par leurs peintures et par la beauté de leur exécution. II. Manuscrits d'origine flamande. *Bibliothèque de l'Ecole des Chartes* 54: 251–326. [CrossRef]
- Espada Custódio, Delmira. 2016. As Perfeitíssimas Horas da rainha D. Leonor. Leitura iconográfica e sua repercussão na deinição do percurso do manuscrito. In *Luz, cor e ouro. Estudos sobre manuscritos iluminados*. Coordinated by Catarina Fernandes Barreira. Lisbon: Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal, pp. 215–34.
- Farquhar, James D. 1976. *Creation and Imitation. The Work of a Fifteenth-Century Manuscript Illuminator*. Florida: Nova/NYIT University Press.
- García García, Francisco de Asis. 2017. Visitación. Base de Datos Digital de Iconografía Medieval. Available online: <https://www.ucm.es/bdiconografiamedieval/visitaci%C3%B3n> (accessed on 30 July 2024).
- García Herrero, María del Carmen. 2015. La dama modélica del Cuatrocientos en la correspondencia de María de Castilla, reina de Aragón (1416–1458). *Cuadernos del CEMyR* 23: 27–48.
- García Herrero, María del Carmen, and Ángela Muñoz Fernández. 2017. Reginalidad y fundaciones monásticas en la Península Ibérica: Un acercamiento al tema. *Edad Media. Revista de Historia* 18: 16–48. [CrossRef]
- Gonzalo Sánchez-Molero, José Luis. 2005. Isabel la Católica: Su influencia en la bibliofilia regia femenina del siglo XVI. In *La reina Isabel y las reinas de España: Realidad, modelos e imagen historiográfica, I*. Coordinated by María Victoria López Cordón and Gloria Ángeles Franco Rubio. Madrid: Fundación Española de Historia Moderna, pp. 157–76.
- González Zymila, Herbert, and Concepción Castillo Blasco. 2016. Una aproximación a la iconografía del Libro de Horas de Isabel la Católica, Ms. II/Tesoro, Real Biblioteca: 4 Imágenes marianas entre el texto bíblico y las leyendas apócrifas. *Mirabilia Ars* 5: 1–47.
- Gómez Anuarbe, Manuel. 2003. Jardines de la cruz. In *Monasterios Románicos y producción artística*. Coordinated by José Ángel García de Cortázar. Aguilar de Campoo: Fundación Santa María la Real, pp. 241–46.
- Gómez-Chacón, Diana Lucía. 2022. Que lo espero en el otro siglo: Pompa, devoción y memoria en las joyas de Isabel I de Castilla. *Visión Doble: Revista de Crítica e Historia del Arte*. Available online: <http://humanidades.uprrp.edu/visiondoble/?p=6249> (accessed on 17 August 2024).
- Gómez del Pulgar Escudero, Lucía. 2004. San Jorge y el dragón en el Libro de Horas de Isabel la Católica. *Emblemata* 10: 127–41.
- Hamburger, Jeffrey F. 2012. Mysticism and Visuality. In *The Cambridge Companion to Christian Mysticism*. Edited by Amy Hollywood and Patricia Z. Beckman. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 277–93.
- Havice, Christine. 1995. Women and the Production of Art in the Middle Ages: The Significance of Context. In *Double Vision: Perspectives on Gender and the Visual Arts*. Edited by Natalie Harris Bluestone. London and Toronto: Fairleigh Dickinson University Press, pp. 67–94.
- Huizinga, Johan. 1996. *The Autumn of the Middle Ages*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Levi d'Ancona, Mirella. 1977. *The Garden of the Renaissance: Botanical Symbolism in Italian Painting*. Florence: Olschki Edizioni.
- López Montilla, María Jesús. 2012. *El Libro de Horas. Un libro selecto de devoción privada*. Madrid: Ediciones de La Ergástula.
- López Serrano, Matilde. 1969. *Libro de Horas de Isabel la Católica*. Madrid: Patrimonio Nacional.
- López-Valdemoro de Quesada, Juan Gualberto. 1910. *Catálogo de la Real Biblioteca, I: Autores-Historia*. Madrid: Sucesores de Rivadeneyra.
- MacKay, Angus. 1987. Don Fernando de Antequera y la Virgen Santa María. In *Homenaje al Profesor Juan Torres Fontes, II*. Murcia: Universidad de Murcia and Real Academia Alfonso X el Sabio, pp. 949–57.
- Martín Martínez de Simón, Elena. 2018. El mundo vegetal en la Edad Media. *Biblioteca: Estudio e Investigación* 33: 47–70.
- Martínez Montes, Luis Francisco. 2022. *Mundos Iluminados. La historia global de España en doce códices extraordinarios*; Madrid: Ministerio de Asuntos Exteriores.
- Morant Gimeno, Ana María. 2018. Las devociones marianas de los reyes de la Corona de Aragón: Reyes protegidos por la Madre de Dios. In *El linaje del Rey Monje. La configuración cultural e iconográfica de la Corona aragonensis (1164–1516)*. Directed Víctor Mínguez Cornelles. Castellon: Universitat Jaume I, pp. 145–60.
- Pascual Molina, Jesús F. 2015. Juan II de Aragón y las artes suntuarias. *Ars Longa* 24: 71–83.
- Peinado Guzmán, José Antonio. 2012. Simbología inmaculista, letanías lauretanas e iconografía. *Archivo Teológico Granadino* 75: 167–90.
- Peirats, Anna, and Rubén Gregori. 2023. Meditation and Contemplation: Word and Image at the Service of Medieval Spirituality. *Religions* 14: 188. [CrossRef]

- Penketh, Sandra. 1997. Women and Books of Hours. In *Women and the Book: Assessing the Visual Evidence*. Edited by Jane Taylor and Leslie Smith. London and Toronto: British Library and Toronto University Press, pp. 266–81.
- Planas Badenas, Josefina. 2015. La paz de las plegarias: Lecturas religiosas de la reina María de Luna. Available online: <https://journals.openedition.org/e-spania/24155> (accessed on 10 September 2024).
- Planas Badenas, Josefina. 2020a. La liturgia en los Libros de Horas de la Corona de Aragón: Plegarias para la misa. In *Patrimonio Textual y Humanidades Digitales II. Libros, bibliotecas y Cultura Visual en la Edad Media*. Directed Pedro M. Cátedra and Juan Miguel Valero. Salamanca: IEMYRhd, pp. 13–42.
- Planas Badenas, Josefina. 2020b. Bajo el signo de Flandes. Libros de Horas iluminados en la Corona de Aragón. *Rivista di storia della Miniatura* 24: 95–108.
- Planas Badenas, Josefina. 2020c. La relación texto-imagen en los libros de horas iluminados en la Corona de Aragón. *Goya. Revista de Arte* 372: 175–91.
- Planas Badenas, Josefina, and Javier Docampo Capilla. 2016. *Horae. El poder de la imagen: Libros de Horas en las bibliotecas españolas*. Madrid: Orbis Mediaevalis.
- Porqueres, Bea. 2013. El Abrazo de María e Isabel o La Visitación. Del afecto y el apoyo entre mujeres. *Investigaciones Feministas* 4: 133–54. [CrossRef]
- Reinburg, Virginia. 2012. *French Books of Hours. Making an Archive of Prayer, c. 1400–1600*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ruiz Domingo, Lledó. 2018. Escribir para construir: La imagen de la reina Juana Enríquez en la correspondencia y la crónica del siglo XV. In *Voces de mujeres en la Edad Media. Entre realidad y ficción*. Edited by Esther Corral Diaz. Berlin and Boston: De Gruyter, pp. 104–10. [CrossRef]
- Ruiz García, Elisa. 2003. Los libros de Isabel la Católica: Una encrucijada de intereses. In *Libro y lectura en la Península Ibérica y América (siglos XIII a XVIII)*. Edited by Antonio Catillo Gómez. España: Junta de Castilla y León, pp. 53–77.
- Ruiz García, Elisa. 2004. Los breviarios de la Reina Católica: Un signo de modernidad. In *III Jornadas científicas sobre Documentación en época de los Reyes Católicos*. Coordinated by José María de Francisco Olmos and Javier de Santiago Fernández. Madrid: Universidad Complutense de Madrid, pp. 221–48.
- Salvador González, José María. 2013. *Flos de radice Iesse*. Aproximación hermenéutica al motivo del lirio en la pintura gótica española de *La Anunciación* a la luz de fuentes patrísticas y teológicas. *Eikón/Imago* 2: 183–222. [CrossRef]
- Salvador González, José María. 2014a. In *virga Aaron Maria ostendebatur*. Nueva interpretación del lirio en *La Anunciación* gótica española a la luz de fuentes patrísticas y teológicas. *Anales de Historia del Arte* 24: 37–60. [CrossRef]
- Salvador González, José María. 2014b. *Flos campi et lilium convallium*. Third interpretation of lily in the iconography of The Annunciation in Italian Trecento art from patristic and theological sources. *Eikón/Imago* 5: 75–96. [CrossRef]
- Salvador González, José María. 2014c. *Sicut lilium inter spinas*. Metáforas florales en la iconografía mariana bajomedieval a la luz de fuentes patrísticas y teológicas. *Eikón/Imago* 3: 1–32. [CrossRef]
- Salvador González, José María. 2015. *Sanctitate vernans virga Aaronis*. Interpretation of the stem of lilies in the medieval iconography of the Annunciation according to theological sources. *Oxford Academic Studies Press. Art Studies and Architectural Journal* 10: 2–32.
- Santos Otero, Aurelio de. 2005. Los Evangelios apócrifos. In *Estudios introductorios y versión de los textos originales por Aurelio de Santos Otero*. Madrid: Biblioteca de Autores Cristianos.
- Steppe, Jan Karel. 1961. Vlaamse kunstwerken in het bezit van Doña Juana Enriquez, echtgenote van Jan II van Aragon en moeder van Ferdinand de Katholieke. In *Scrinium Lovaniense. Mélanges historiques—Historische Opstellen Etienne Van Cauwenbergh*. Gembloux: J. Duculot, pp. 301–30.
- Universidad de Navarra. 2018. *Sagrada Biblia. Comentario*. Navarra: Eunsa.
- Van den Gheyn, Joseph. 1906. Notes sur quelques manuscrits à miniatures de l'école flamande conservés dans les bibliothèques d'Espagne. *Annales de l'Académie royale d'archéologie de Belgique* 58: 321–24.
- Velu, Anne-Marie. 2012. *La Visitation dans l'art. Orient et Occident. Ve-XVIe siècle*. Paris: Éditions du Cerf.
- Verheyden, Joseph. 2011. Creating Different Through Parallelism: Luke's Handling of the Traditions of John the Baptist and Jesus in the Infancy Narrative. In *Infancy Gospels: Stories and Identities*. Edited by Claire Clivaz, Andreas Dettwiler, Luc Devillers, Enrico Norelli and Benjamin Bertho. Germany: Mohr Siebeck, pp. 137–60.
- Voragine, Jacobus de. 1982. *La Leyenda Dorada I*. Madrid: Alianza Editorial.
- Westergård, Ira. 2006. Which Narrative? The Case of the Narrative Subject in Fifteenth-Century Altarpieces. In *The Travelling Concept of Narrative*. Edited by Matti Hyvärinen, Anu Korhonen and Juri Mykkänenpp. Helsinki: Helsinki Collegium for Advanced Studies, pp. 60–83.
- Westergård, Ira. 2007. *Approaching Sacred Pregnancy: The Cult of the Visitation and Narrative Altarpieces in Late Fifteenth-Century Florence*. Helsinki: Suomalaisen Kirjallisuuden Seura.
- Zalama, Miguel Ángel, and Jesús Pascual Molina. 2012. Tapices de Juan II de Aragón y Fernando el Católico en La Seo de Zaragoza. *Boletín del Museo e Instituto Camón Aznar* 109: 285–20.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.